

SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND PHOTOCATALYTIC BEHAVIOR OF TiO₂ AND TiO₂/WO₃ FIBERS

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Summary

The degradation of organic contaminants by heterogeneous photocatalysis is a promising option to replace conventional water treatment systems. The most used semiconductor in photocatalysis is TiO₂ due to some specific characteristics, such as: efficiency, stability, low toxicity and insolubility in water. However, TiO₂ has its photocatalytic capabilities activated by only 3% of the solar spectrum. The doping of TiO₂ with other semiconductor metals is an alternative to increase its photoactivity. In this work, TiO₂ and TiO₂ fibers mixed with tungstic acid (H₂WO₄) were obtained by *electrospinning*, characterized by: X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and photodegradation tests of 125 mL of a 20 ppm solution of methyl orange dye. The results indicate that the photocatalytic properties of the fibers were influenced by: heat treatment temperature, band gap reduction and position of the conduction band of WO₃ in relation to TiO₂, which inhibited the recombination of the electron/hole pair, allowing the transfer of charges between the two semiconductors, increasing the efficiency of the process.

Keywords: fibers, photodegradation, TiO₂, WO₃, semiconductors.

Abstract

The degradation of organic contaminants by heterogeneous photocatalysis is a promising option to replace conventional water treatment systems. The most used semiconductor in photocatalysis is TiO₂ due to some specific characteristics, such as: efficiency, stability, low toxicity and insolubility in water. However, TiO₂ has its photocatalytic capabilities activated by only 3% of the solar spectrum. The doping of TiO₂ with other semiconductor metals is an alternative to increase its photoactivity. In this work, TiO₂ and TiO₂ fibers mixed with tungstic acid (H₂WO₄) were obtained by electrospinning, characterized by: X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and photodegradation tests of 125 mL of a 20 ppm solution of methyl orange dye. The results indicate that the photocatalytic properties of the fibers were influenced by: heat treatment temperature, band gap reduction and position of the

conduction band of WO_3 in relation to TiO_2 , which inhibited the recombination of the electron/hole pair, allowing the transfer of charges between the two semiconductors, increasing the efficiency of the process.

Keywords: fibers, photodegradation, TiO_2 , WO_3 , semiconductors.

1. Introduction

Advanced Oxidative Processes (POA'S) can be divided into homogeneous and heterogeneous processes. Its functioning basis resides in the generation of hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$), with high oxidizing power, and in the complete mineralization of several organic compounds through the reaction with this radical. These processes have attracted attention, for example, due to the increase in complexity and difficulty in treating wastewater, which has been the reason for the search for new methodologies aimed at remediating these tailings. The action of hydroxyl radicals occurs by addition to the double bond or by removing the hydrogen atom in aliphatic organic molecules. Oxidants such as ozone and hydrogen peroxide, associated with ultraviolet (UV) or visible (Vis) radiation and catalysts or semiconductors, are reactions responsible for the formation of hydroxyl radicals [1].

Photocatalysis is an advanced oxidative process that through the action of a photocatalyst increases the rate of a reaction. These chemical reactions are caused by the absorption of photons of ultraviolet, visible or infrared light by compounds (photocatalysts) that are capable of generating free radicals, such as hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$). These can be generated through the use of photochemical processes with ultraviolet radiation, in association with the absorption of radiation by a semiconductor, generating the electron/hole pair $[(e^-)/(h^+)]$ in its electronic structure. The photogenerated species give rise to the formation of redox reactions [1].

TiO_2 is the most used semiconductor in photocatalytic processes due to its excellent photoactivity, abundance in nature, being economically viable and easy to process [1].

Therefore, this work intends to show the optical and photocatalytic behavior of titanium and tungsten oxide fibers, when irradiated by UVA light, aiming to increase the applicability of TiO_2 as a photocatalyst in the visible range. Because it has a high *band gap*.

2. Experimental

2.1 Electrospinning

Fibers were obtained by preparing 2 precursor solutions. The TiO_2 solution was obtained by mixing 2.5 ml of titanium propoxide (TIP), 2.0 ml of glacial acetic acid and 5.0 ml

of an alcoholic solution containing 10% by weight of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP). The TiO_2 / WO_3 solution was prepared by mixing the above mentioned reagents with 1 ml of hydrogen peroxide and 0.10 g of H_2WO_4 , which were kept under magnetic stirring for 15 minutes. Then, a plastic syringe was charged with 5 mL of the TiO_2 or TiO_2 / WO_3 precursor solution which was connected to a hypodermic stainless steel feeding needle by a high voltage source. The distance between the capillary tube and the cylindrical collector was 12 cm, the voltage was 13.5 kV with a flow of 1.8 mL/h. The cylindrical collector was covered with aluminum foil to collect the fibers produced every 30 minutes for a period of 4 hours. The fibers were heat treated in an electric oven (SANCHIS) at 650 °C, 700 °C, 750 °C or 800 °C with a 1 h threshold and a heating rate of 1.4 °C/min.

2.2 Characterization

A PHILIPS diffractometer with CuK α radiation, with a voltage of 40 kV and 40 mA, equipped with the X'PERT HighScore software, was used to identify the phases present in the fibers. A scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL 6060) equipped with EDS (energy dispersive spectroscopy), used to assess fiber morphology and identify the presence of W, Ti and O atoms in the samples, depending on fiber composition. The equipment used to measure band gap energy was a dual-beam UV-vis-NIR spectrophotometer (Cary 5000), with an integrating sphere in diffuse light reflection mode. Band gap energy values were obtained through the Kubelka and Munk correlation. The photocatalytic performance of TiO_2 and TiO_2 / WO_3 samples was analyzed by changing the concentration of methyl orange dye under UVA irradiation. To carry out the photocatalysis tests, 0.25 g of the fibers in question were mixed with 125 ml of a solution containing 20 ppm of methyl orange. This mixture was transferred to a photocatalytic reactor and the UV light system was turned on. Before the beginning of each assay, a 4 mL aliquot of the solution was collected, defined as the initial reference sample (absorbance indicative of a concentration equal to 100% methyl orange; reaction time of zero minutes). This first aliquot was removed before the application of the light system, water circulation and air bubbling. During the test, with the UVA light system on, 4 mL aliquots of the solution were removed with a plastic syringe at 15-minute intervals, filtered through 0.2 μm filters and placed in polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) cuvettes. to then be analyzed by a spectrophotometer (Cary 5000, Agilent, with UMA accessory).

3. Results and discussion

Figure 1 shows the diffractogram of the fibers obtained by electrospinning. The samples without heat treatment (STT) were amorphous for both formulations. The TiO_2 fibers (Figure 1a) treated up to a temperature of $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ showed only the presence of the anatase crystalline phase (JCPDS 010782486), with the first characteristic peak at approximately $2\theta = 25.271^\circ$. The fibers treated from $750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ showed, in addition to the anatase phase, the rutile phase (JCPDS 01-077-0442), with the first characteristic peak at approximately $2\theta = 27.294^\circ$, resulting from the occurrence of a phase transition of TiO_2 , predicted after increasing the heat treatment temperature [2,3]. In TiO_2/WO_3 fibers (Figure 1b) treated up to $650\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, anatase (JCPDS 01-078-2486) and brookite (JCPDS 01-075-1582) phases were identified for TiO_2 with characteristic peaks at approximately $2\theta = 25.271^\circ$ and 25.425° , respectively. In the fibers treated from $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ onwards, TiO_2 showed the anatase, brookite and rutile phases (JCPDS 01-077-0442), with the first characteristic peak at approximately $2\theta = 27.294^\circ$. For WO_3 the monoclinic phase (JCPDS 00-032-1393) appeared at all heat treatment temperatures, with the first characteristic peak at approximately $2\theta = 23^\circ$.

(a) (b)

Figure 1. Diffractogram of (a) TiO_2 and (b) TiO_2/WO_3 samples .

Figure 2 (ab) shows the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the surface of TiO_2 and TiO_2/WO_3 fibers , heat treated at $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. From the images, it is noted that the TiO_2 and TiO_2/WO_3 fibers appear to be similar in morphology, they seem to be made up of an agglomerate of particles primary, with an elongated, continuous shape and without a preferential orientation.

Figure 2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of (a) TiO_2 and (b) TiO_2/WO_3 samples treated at 800°C .

Figure 3 (ab) shows the photocatalytic activity of TiO_2 and TiO_2/WO_3 fibers in the degradation of methyl orange dye during 135 minutes of exposure to UVA light ($\lambda = 365 \text{ nm}$). All fibers showed photocatalytic activity. The most photoactive TiO_2 fibers were those that received heat treatment at 650°C , were able to degrade approximately 40% of the methyl orange dye in 135 minutes of UVA irradiation. The fibers treated at 700°C and the P25 standard had a similar behavior, degrading approximately 30% of the dye in 135 minutes of UVA irradiation. And the fibers treated at 750°C and 800°C , degraded approximately 20% and 10%, respectively, of the dye in 135 minutes of UVA irradiation. This decrease observed in the photoactivity of the samples is the result of the formation of the rutile phase, which in the case of fibers arises from treatments above 700°C . The rutile phase is less photoactive than the anatase phase and, for this reason, its appearance reduces the photocatalytic activity of the synthesized fibers [2,3]. The presence of tungsten in the TiO_2/WO_3 samples increased the photocatalytic activity of the fibers treated at temperatures of 700°C , 750°C and 800°C , to approximately 36%, 50% and 90% of degradation, respectively. Such effectiveness is due; band gap reduction from 3.05 eV to 2.89 eV, inhibition of the recombination of the electron/hole pair $[(e^-)/(h^+)]$, which allowed the transfer of charges between TiO_2 and WO_3 , and the increase in the formation of point defects (O_2 vacancies). The increase in the heat treatment temperature made it possible for the O_2 vacancies to acquire the necessary mobility to move to a disordered state in the network, increasing the degradation capacity and the process efficiency [4,5,6].

(a) (b)

Figure 3. Photocatalytic activity of TiO₂-P25 and fibers in the degradation of the relative concentration of the methyl orange dye: (a) TiO₂ and (b) TiO₂/WO₃.

4. Conclusions

The results obtained by the samples synthesized when using them in photocatalysis is due to the synchronicity between the chemical and physical properties of titanium and tungsten oxides, due to the reduction in their *band gap* and the increase in the heat treatment temperature, which made it possible for the O₂ vacancies acquire the necessary mobility to move to a disordered state in the network, increasing the ability to degrade and absorb light. The presence of tungsten increased the photocatalytic efficiency of the materials, inhibited the recombination of the electron/hole pair [(e⁻)/(h⁺)], allowing charge transfer between TiO₂ and WO₃.

Thanks

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